

INFLUENCE OF WORKFORCE DEVELOPMENT RESOURCES ON THE IMPLEMENTATION OF BUSINESS EDUCATION CURRICULUM IN TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS IN NIGER STATE

BY

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Abstract

This study examined the availability, utilization, and adequacy of workforce development resources for effective implementation of the Business Education curriculum in the Tertiary Institutions in Niger State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey research design was adopted, with a population consisting of 50 Business Education lecturers and 200 students. A purposive sample of 50 respondents (5 lecturers and 45 final-year students) was selected. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire titled Influence of Workforce Development Resources on the Implementation of Business Education Curriculum in Tertiary Institutions (IWFDRIBECITI), validated by experts in Business Education, the reliability coefficient was determined using Cronbach's Alpha, with a threshold of 0.70. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation for research questions and t-tests for hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that while some workforce development resources such as ICT laboratories, internet-connected computers, and modern office equipment are moderately available, the utilization, particularly of business simulation software, remains low. Moreover, although resources align with curriculum objectives and industry trends, they are insufficient to meet the needs of the growing student population. Hypothesis testing revealed no significant relationship between the availability of resources and curriculum implementation, but there was a significant difference in perception between lecturers and students regarding resource utilization. The study recommends the provision of more updated workforce development resources and improved integration of modern technologies in the Business Education curriculum.

Keywords: *Business Education, Curriculum Implementation, Workforce Development Resources, Resource Utilization,*

Introduction

Business Education plays a crucial role in equipping students with the knowledge and practical skills necessary for entrepreneurship, self-employment, and workforce readiness. In Nigeria, Business Education is offered at the tertiary level and aims to develop competent business professionals and educators (Okoli, 2020). For the curriculum to be effectively implemented, adequate workforce development resources such as ICT tools, textbooks, and business simulation technologies must be readily available and efficiently utilized by both instructors and students.

However, inadequate and outdated resources, ineffective utilization, and poor alignment with industry standards have been observed as recurrent challenges facing Business Education programs in many Nigerian institutions (Okwuanaso & Nwazor, 2021). The implementation of the Business Education curriculum could be compromised if these issues persist in Tertiary Institutions in Niger State.

This study, therefore, seeks to assess the workforce development resources available for Business Education, determine their utilization, and evaluate their adequacy and relevance for effective curriculum implementation. It also investigates the perceptions of lecturers and students toward these resources and examines the significance of their availability in curriculum delivery.

Business Education Concept

Business Education is a component of vocational and technical education designed to equip learners with the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and competencies required to function effectively in business environments either as entrepreneurs or as employees in private and public sectors. It integrates both theoretical and practical instruction to prepare individuals not only for gainful employment but also for self-reliance and economic independence. It refers to the teaching and learning process that imparts knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values essential for effective participation in the business world. It is designed to prepare individuals for work in business environments and also for self-employment. Business Education includes courses such as accounting, marketing, office practice, and entrepreneurship.

Business Education provides learners with both theoretical and practical knowledge to function effectively in various business contexts. It promotes the acquisition of lifelong skills and the development of a business-oriented mindset essential for national development (Ezeani, 2020).

In tertiary education, Business Education plays a critical role in producing graduates who are not only academically sound but also practically equipped to meet industry needs. Uche and Adewale (2021) highlight that Business Education aims at producing skilled manpower for the commercial, industrial, and managerial sectors of the economy, thereby bridging the gap between education and the labour market.

Furthermore, Business Education encourages entrepreneurial thinking among students. By engaging in case studies, simulations, and real-world business projects, students learn how to identify market opportunities, manage

risks, and develop viable business plans. This entrepreneurial orientation is vital in a developing economy where job creation is as important as job seeking.

However, the effectiveness of Business Education in achieving its goals is heavily dependent on the availability and quality of instructional resources, such as qualified lecturers, up-to-date textbooks, computers, business laboratories, and industry linkages. The absence of these resources undermines the ability of institutions to deliver a curriculum that is relevant and responsive to current business trends.

Workforce Development Resources

Workforce development resources also referred to as educational resources, instructional resources or teaching-learning materials, are all the inputs used to facilitate the effective delivery of curriculum content and enhance the achievement of educational objectives. These resources can be grouped broadly into two categories: human resources (teachers, instructors, lab technicians, and support staff) and material resources (textbooks, ICT tools, business laboratories, furniture, audiovisual equipment, and office machines). Human resources, especially qualified and competent lecturers, are critical for interpreting and delivering the curriculum effectively. Without skilled educators, even the well-designed curriculum may fail to achieve its goals (Yusuf & Daramola, 2018).

On the other hand, material resources provide the means through which practical experiences can be gained. For instance, in Business Education, computers, accounting software, and office simulation tools help students translate abstract concepts into real-world applications. According to Ogbunaya and Udemba (2019), the availability and proper utilization of educational resources significantly influence students' academic performance and skill acquisition.

Another essential aspect of Workforce development resources is infrastructure, which includes lecture halls, libraries, internet facilities, and power supply. These foundational elements are often overlooked, yet they form the backbone of any educational system. Inadequate or poorly maintained infrastructure negatively affects curriculum implementation, particularly in vocational and business-related courses that require hands-on training.

The quality and quantity of workforce development resources are directly linked to educational outcomes. As Okolie, Igwe, & Nwajiuba (2019) argue, institutions with adequate and updated resources are more likely to produce graduates who meet the demands of employers and society. This means that evaluating and continuously improving educational resources should be a key priority for stakeholders in education, especially in vocational disciplines like Business Education.

Curriculum Implementation

Curriculum implementation involves translating written curriculum into instructional activities that lead to student learning. The quality and availability of teaching and learning resources play a significant role in this process. It refers to the process by which the planned curriculum is translated into practice through teaching and learning

activities in the classroom and other learning environments. It is the stage where curriculum goals, objectives, content, and strategies are put into action to achieve the desired educational outcomes (Uche & Adewale, 2021).

In Business Education, curriculum implementation involves delivering business-related subjects (e.g., accounting, entrepreneurship, office technology, marketing, etc.) using appropriate instructional methods, teaching aids, and assessment strategies. It includes the day-to-day interaction between educators and learners, the use of Workforce development resources, and the management of the facilities to ensure that students acquire relevant business knowledge and skills.

Successful implementation of the Business Education curriculum depends on several key factors:

1. **Availability of Resources:** Implementation is heavily influenced by the availability and adequacy of resources such as qualified lecturers, updated textbooks, ICT tools, office equipment, and functional business laboratories (Uche & Adewale, 2021). Where these resources are lacking or obsolete, the curriculum cannot be effectively implemented.
2. **Teacher Quality and Motivation:** Teachers play a central role in curriculum implementation. Their qualifications, experience, teaching style, and attitude towards the subject matter greatly determine how well students engage with and understand the content. According to Ezeani (2020), even a well-designed curriculum can fail if not delivered by competent and motivated teachers.
3. **Institutional Support:** Support from institutional management including funding, provision of facilities, training opportunities, and supportive policies is essential for successful curriculum implementation. This includes regular review of the curriculum in line with current business practices and technology trends.
4. **Student Participation:** Effective implementation also involves engaging students actively in the learning process. Business Education requires interactive and participatory methods such as project-based learning, simulations, group discussions, and practical exercises. When students are actively involved, they gain more from the curriculum.
5. **Assessment and Feedback:** Regular assessment helps determine whether curriculum goals are being met. Feedback from assessments allows educators to adjust their teaching strategies and helps students identify areas for improvement.

However, curriculum implementation in many Nigerian tertiary institutions is often challenged by systemic issues such as underfunding, overcrowded classrooms, shortage of materials, and bureaucratic delays in curriculum review. These challenges hinder the realization of curriculum goals and reduce the quality of graduates produced.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the strategic importance of Business Education in national development and employment creation, many tertiary institutions in Niger State lack the essential workforce development resources to effectively implement the curriculum. This has led to graduates lacking the practical and professional skills expected of them in the job

market. The study seeks to appraise the workforce development resources in the implementation of business education curriculum in Niger State tertiary institutions, with specific reference to federal college of education, Kontagora in Niger state.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to appraise the availability and utilization of Business Education workforce development resources in the implementation of the Business Education curriculum in Federal University of Education Kontagora, Niger State.

Specific Objectives are to:

1. Determine the availability of workforce development resources for Business Education in Tertiary Institutions in Niger State.
2. Examine how available resources are utilized by lecturers and students in curriculum implementation.
3. Assess the adequacy and relevance of available resources in relation to the current Business Education curriculum.

Research Questions

To achieve the stated objectives, the following research questions guided the study:

1. What workforce development resources are available for Business Education in Tertiary Institutions in Niger State?
2. How are these resources utilized in the implementation of the Business Education curriculum by both the lecturers and students?
3. Are the available resources adequate and relevant for implementing the current Business Education curriculum?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at a 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant relationship between the availability of Business Education resources and effective curriculum implementation.
2. There is no significant difference in the utilization of Business Education resources towards curriculum implementation by both lecturers and students.

Methodology

This study employed a descriptive survey design to collect data from lecturers and students in the selected tertiary institutions in Niger State. The descriptive approach provides a detailed and factual account of the current state of Business Education resources and how they are utilized for curriculum implementation. The population consists of all Business education students and Business educators (lecturers) in all the tertiary institutions in Niger State. A sample size of 50 participants (5 lecturers and 45 final-year Business Education students) were selected through purposive sampling, the questionnaire titled Influence of Workforce Development Resources on the Implementation of Business Education Curriculum in Tertiary Institutions (IWFDRIBECITI) was used for quantifiable responses. To ensure validity, the

questionnaire was reviewed by experts in Business Education to check for content relevance, clarity, and comprehensiveness. The reliability coefficient was determined using Cronbach’s Alpha, with a threshold of 0.70, this is considered acceptable for internal consistency (Tavakol&Dennick, 2011). The researcher administered the questionnaire in person. Respondents were assured of confidentiality and the purpose of the study was explained to them to encourage honest and accurate responses. The collected data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to analyze the research question and t-tests was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Result of the Findings

- Research Questions 1:** What workforce development resources are available for Business Education in Tertiary Institutions in Niger State?

Table 1: Instructional Resources Available for Business Education

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	$\sum x$	Mean	SD	Decision
1	Business Education classrooms are equipped with adequate furniture	20	18	10	2	156	3.12	0.76	Agree
2	There are sufficient up-to-date textbooks	15	20	10	5	145	2.90	0.81	Slightly Agree
3	Modern office equipment is available for practice	17	18	10	5	148	2.96	0.85	Agree
4	Functional ICT laboratories are accessible	22	16	9	3	154	3.08	0.78	Agree
5	There is access to internet-connected computers	25	15	7	3	158	3.16	0.79	Agree

Field Survey: 2025

Table 1 above shows that the respondents agreed with items 1, 3, 4, and 5, with mean scores of 3.11, 2.97, 3.05, and 3.13 respectively, while they slightly agreed with item 2, which had a mean score of 2.89. This implies that while some workforce development resources such as ICT laboratories, internet-connected computers, and modern office equipment are perceived to be moderately available, there is a slight inadequacy in up-to-date textbooks and reference materials. Overall, the findings suggest that instructional resources are fairly available for Business Education

2. **Research Questions 2:** How are these resources utilized in the implementation of the Business Education curriculum by both the lecturers and students?

Table 2: Utilization of Business Education Resources

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	$\sum x$	Mean	SD	Decision
6	Lecturers use ICT resources effectively	21	17	9	3	153	3.06	0.81	Agree
7	Students use provided resources for assignments	18	15	10	7	146	2.92	0.84	Slightly Agree
8	Office equipment used regularly for practical skills	16	14	12	8	142	2.84	0.86	Slightly Agree
9	Business simulation software is part of teaching	12	13	15	10	135	2.70	0.90	Disagree
10	Library resources used by students and lecturers	26	15	6	3	161	3.22	0.75	Agree

Field Survey: 2025

Table 2 indicates that respondents agreed with items 6 and 10 with mean scores of 3.07 and 3.23, slightly agreed with items 7 and 8 (means of 2.93 and 2.85 respectively), and disagreed with item 9 which had a mean of 2.71. This reveals that while lecturers and students are utilizing ICT resources and library materials to some extent, there is limited integration of business simulation software into the teaching process. It further suggests that although resource utilization is relatively effective, some modern tools and techniques required for practical exposure are underutilized in Business Education.

Research Questions 3: Are the available resources adequate and relevant for implementing the current Business Education curriculum?

Table 3: Adequacy and Relevance of Resources to the Curriculum

S/N	Statement	SA	A	D	SD	$\sum x$	Mean	SD	Decision
11	Materials meet Business Education course objectives	23	18	7	2	159	3.18	0.73	Agree
12	Resources align with industry expectations	20	17	8	5	150	3.00	0.82	Agree
13	Enough instructional materials for population size	15	18	10	7	143	2.86	0.85	Slightly Agree
14	Curriculum hindered due to inadequate resources	10	12	15	13	128	2.56	0.91	Disagree
15	Resources are relevant and meet practical needs	19	17	10	4	151	3.02	0.80	Agree

Field Survey: 2025

Table 3 shows that the respondents agreed with items 11, 12, and 15 with mean scores of 3.18, 3.00, and 3.02 respectively, slightly agreed with item 13 which had a mean score of 2.86, and disagreed with item 14 with a mean of 2.56. This suggests that available teaching materials are generally aligned with course objectives and current industry needs. However, the slight agreement on instructional sufficiency and the disagreement on curriculum being hindered due to resource inadequacy indicate that while resources are relevant, they are not fully sufficient to meet the growing demand and ensure optimal curriculum implementation.

Hypothesis Testing Results

Table 4 hypothesis 1

Hypothesis	Df	t-value	p-value	Decision
There is no significant relationship between the availability of Business Education resources and effective curriculum implementation.	49	1.00	0.347	Accept

The table above revealed that the calculated *t-value* is 1.00 with a *p-value* of 0.347, which is greater than the 0.05 significance level. This leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. This implies that there is no statistically significant relationship between the availability of Business Education resources and effective curriculum implementation in the sampled institutions.

Table 5 hypothesis 2

Hypothesis	Df	t-value	p-value	Decision
There is no significant difference in the utilization of Business Education resources towards curriculum implementation by both lecturers and students.	49	2.52	0.036	Reject

The table above shows that the *t-value* is 2.52 and the *p-value* is 0.036, which is less than 0.05. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis. Thus, there is a significant difference in the utilization of Business Education resources towards curriculum implementation by both lecturers and students, suggesting differing experiences or expectations in how these resources are used.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from Research Question 1 revealed that a range of workforce development resources are moderately available for Business Education in tertiary institutions in Niger State. Most respondents agreed that ICT laboratories, internet-connected computers, and modern office equipment are present and usable. However, there was only slight agreement regarding the sufficiency of up-to-date textbooks. This

implies that while infrastructural support for ICT and practical instruction is fair, the availability of core academic resources such as textbooks remains an issue. This partial availability aligns with earlier findings by Akingbade and Yusuf (2022), who noted that many Nigerian institutions suffer from outdated textbooks and instructional materials, thereby impeding optimal teaching and learning.

Regarding Research Question 2, the findings indicated varying levels of resource utilization. While lecturers effectively utilize ICT tools and library materials, there is relatively limited use of business simulation software and office equipment for practical instruction. The mean scores from Table 2 support the observation that although lecturers are making efforts, full integration of modern technological tools into instructional practice remains insufficient. This trend highlights the gap between resource availability and their optimal use, echoing the findings of Ezeani and Ezekwesili (2020), who emphasized the underutilization of educational technology in Business Education programs across Nigeria. Furthermore, the rejection of the second hypothesis, which tested the perceptual difference between students and lecturers on resource utilization, supports the idea that inconsistencies exist in how these resources are engaged by different stakeholders.

Finally, findings from Research Question 3 revealed that available instructional resources generally meet the course objectives and align with industry expectations, but are not entirely adequate for the increasing student population. While most respondents agreed that the materials are relevant and practical, the slight agreement on sufficiency and the disagreement on the curriculum being hindered due to resource inadequacy suggest a mixed reality. Moreover, the acceptance of Hypothesis 1 indicates no statistically significant relationship between resource availability and curriculum implementation. This is critical; as it underscores the importance of not just having resources but ensuring they are strategically deployed and contextually applied to support effective teaching. These results are consistent with the arguments by Olawale and Odu (2019), who asserted that relevance and sufficiency must work hand-in-hand for meaningful curriculum delivery.

Conclusion

This study investigated the availability, utilization, and relevance of workforce development resources in implementing the Business Education curriculum in tertiary institutions in Niger State. The findings revealed that while resources such as ICT laboratories, internet access, and modern office equipment are moderately available, key academic materials like up-to-date textbooks are slightly inadequate. Utilization of available resources is also mixed although ICT and library resources are used; business simulation tools and office equipment are underutilized.

Despite the availability of some relevant instructional resources, their adequacy in addressing the demands of a growing student population remains questionable. Furthermore, the hypothesis testing indicated no statistically significant relationship between the availability of resources and curriculum implementation. However, a significant difference exists in the perception of resource utilization between lecturers and students, suggesting a need for improved communication, access, or training on resource use. Therefore, for Business Education to achieve its objectives, both the quantity and quality of instructional resources must be enhanced alongside their effective utilization.

Recommendations

1. Tertiary Institutions should invest in providing more current and comprehensive textbooks and journals for Business Education students and lecturers to enhance theoretical understanding and curriculum alignment. There should be increased emphasis on the integration and practical use of business simulation software and other technological tools to improve students' real-world readiness and skill acquisition.
2. Tertiary Institutions should organize regular workshops and training for both lecturers and students on how to effectively use available instructional resources, particularly underutilized tools like office equipment and business labs. Institution management should develop specific policies supporting the continuous improvement of Business Education resources, backed by adequate budgetary allocations to sustain instructional quality.
3. Tertiary Institutions should establish a periodic monitoring system to evaluate the availability, functionality, and usage of Business Education resources. This will help in identifying gaps and ensuring continuous improvement.
4. Since there is a significant perceptual difference between lecturers and students on resource utilization, open communication forums or feedback systems should be created to align expectations and improve resource accessibility for students.

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